

POLITICAL RAMIFICATIONS OF CULTURE WARS IN THE US: THE CASE OF ABORTION RIGHTS

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Abstract

Culture Wars in the US, often characterised as conflicts between traditionalists and progressives, reflect the deep ideological divisions that exist in the American society. The case of abortion rights in the US is one such divisive issue and has been the subject of protracted political debate and discussion. The US Supreme Court, on 24 June 2022, overturned Roe v. Wade, a historic decision that established a constitutional right to abortion in every state. Consequently, Americans were left more divided and polarised than ever with pro-choice and pro-life supporters on either end of the spectrum. This polarisation of opinion is very stark among the Democrats and Republicans, the two major political parties in the US, and their extreme ideological differences on the issue have a direct bearing on the country's the political system.

The issue has also been gaining steam in recent years as a result of the appointment of conservative judges to the US Supreme Court and the adoption of stringent abortion legislation in many states. In this context, this paper seeks to trace the evolution of culture wars in the US and its impact on the political system. Furthermore, it attempts to analyse abortion rights from a political perspective. Lastly, it tries to assess the impact of the issue on federalism, separation of powers, and the party system in the US.

Keywords: Culture Wars, Abortion Rights, Political Polarisation, American Politics, Roe v. Wade.

Evolution of Culture Wars in the US.

Cultural wars in America have deep historical roots and can be attributed to the organising principle of American pluralism. At its onset, the

conflict involved Protestants, Catholics, Jews, and Mormons, forming an important part of the American heritage. As religious tolerance expanded, the conflict took a new shape and pitted orthodoxy against progressivism. These polarising impulses towards a particular community led to cultural realignment and the formation of pragmatic alliances across different faiths and religious traditions to exert influence in American culture.

Since America was colonised by emigrated Europeans who were predominantly Protestants, anti-Catholic sentiments became woven into its political and cultural fabric and were witnessed predominantly since the nineteenth century (Hunter, 1991, p.36). In the mid-nineteenth century, anti-Catholicism also acted as a precursor to the great school wars in Philadelphia, Boston, and New York. As a result, cultural conflict in America now also played out in schools where the majority dominated and asserted their power over the minority, who were often silenced. There was difficulty in mobilising funds to establish Catholic educational institutions, and Catholic religious instruction was banned in schools. The refusal to accommodate Catholic interests further exacerbated the cultural divide in America during the time.

During the 1840s, 1850s, and 1860s, the strongest manifestation of opposition towards Catholicism was evident in the form of anti-Catholic organisations and political groups (Hunter, 1991, p.37). Many anti-Catholic societies, such as the Christian Alliance, the American Protestant Association, the American and Foreign Christian Union, the American Alliance, and the American Protective Association, existed at the time. The Native American parties of the 1840s, the Know-Nothing party of the 1850s, and the Republican party of the 1850s and 1860s were among the anti-Catholic political parties. They found widespread support and success in states with a high Catholic population and mobilised electoral opinion against them (Hunter, 1991, p.37). As a consequence, the growing Catholic community in America found itself powerless and underprivileged.

The Jews were also victims of this inter-religious hostility in America during the nineteenth century. Even though the vestiges of Puritan culture in America identified with the Old Testament's portrayal of a people "in covenant with God" and had a strong compassion for them, their hardships were seen as justifiable penalties meted out by a wrath

God to a people who had disobeyed His will (Hunter, 1991, p.38). The Jews were strongly criticised for their economic behaviour and were stereotyped as excessively greedy Shylocks who practiced unscrupulous trade. There was a growing concern about the “Hebrew conquest of the financial centres of New York” (Hunter, 1991, p.38). However, anti-Semitism remained a lesser politicised issue in America than anti-Catholicism.

The Mormons also found themselves entangled in the American culture war ever since the formation of the Mormon Church in 1830. In several states in the South, they were harassed and persecuted. A case in point is the killing of Joseph Smith and his brothers in Illinois in 1844 by a mob after being imprisoned. Moreover, the governor of Missouri in 1838 went on to explicitly state that the Mormons must be treated as adversaries and driven out of the state if necessary to secure the interest of the general public (Hunter, 1991, p.39). Mormon missionaries and others faced a similar fate and became victims of murder and violence.

Even though religious and cultural conflict forms an important part of American cultural heritage, it is far removed from contemporary America. With the expansion of religious tolerance in America, the hostility towards Catholics, Jews, and other groups declined. The various religious groups started following a policy of neutrality or mutual indifference towards each other in the 1960s (Hunter, 1991, p.40). This can be demonstrated by the fact that in 1958, 25 per cent of Americans claimed to be opposed to a Catholic presidential candidate, while in 1987, the figure dropped to 8 per cent (Hunter, 1991, p.40).

The origins of the contemporary culture wars in America can be traced back to the 1960s with the rise of counterculture, anti-war, feminist, and civil rights movements. They challenged traditional cultural values and norms, which created a backlash from those who felt threatened by these changes. As a reaction, the “New Right” emerged in the 1980s, which sought to restore traditional values and defend them against progressive challenges. Thus, with these developments, culture wars in America shifted from their original religious roots and began to impact both religious and non-religious Americans (Hunter, 1991, p.46).

Before the 1960s, the unconventional teachings of radical artists, intellectuals, and politicians had mostly failed to reach normative Americans, who still believed in God, hard labour, American

exceptionalism, and gender roles (Snyder, 2015). However, the situation changed in the 1960s and there was widespread conflict, split, and dissent. The emergence of the “New Left” led to a significant reshaping of American culture by drawing attention to issues such as racism, gender, and sexuality. For many in the “New Right”, this cultural revolution was an “abomination” and an attack on some of America’s most cherished values and beliefs (Snyder, 2015).

In the 1970s, the rise of neoconservatives and Christian evangelicals served as a training ground for culture wars in America. Neoconservatives attacked affirmative action, the welfare state, and identity politics while promoting colour-blind social policies and a positive view of America (Snyder, 2015). Christian evangelicals like Jerry Falwell rallied around “family values”, while Phyllis Schlafly led the movement against the Equal Rights Amendment (ERA), whose campaign was successful in preventing its ratification. Feminist Betty Friedan criticised Schlafly, and her remarks anticipated the bitter exchanges of future culture wars (Hartman, 2015, p.90). Religion, gender, sexuality, and race were the contested fronts of this conflict, and the debates ranged from disagreements over social progress to the demotion of the male breadwinner.

One of the earliest flashpoints in the contemporary American culture wars was the debate over abortion, which was ignited by the landmark 1973 Supreme Court decision in *Roe v. Wade* that legalised abortion nationwide. Many evangelicals, like the majority of Americans, had ambivalent opinions about abortion before it was legalised. However, some far-right preachers, such as John Rice, viewed the legalisation of abortion as the “latest liberal assault on morality in a rapidly escalating cultural war” (Hartman, 2015, p.93). Consequently, pro-life and pro-choice groups emerged, with each side arguing for their position based on moral, religious, and legal grounds.

Furthermore, in the 1980s, the issue of gay rights emerged as a major source of contention with the emergence of the AIDS epidemic and the fight for equal rights for LGBTQ individuals. The Moral Majority, a conservative Christian group, actively opposed LGBTQ rights along with other social issues like sex education and pornography. The group gained influence after being identified as crucial to Ronald Reagan’s presidential victory. These events greatly disturbed the liberals, who

equated the Christian Right to the Iranian radicals who had kidnapped Americans (Hartman, 2015, p.100). With organisations like Focus on the Family and the Family Research Council promoting conservative social policies and values, the Christian Right emerged as a significant political force in the 1990s.

The notion of a national struggle over values and ideas was made prominent during Patrick Buchanan's 1992 presidential campaign, which warned of a "culture war" for the soul of America. In one of his well-known essays, he issues a cautionary note against the Marxist threat to American culture. Thus, by that time, American conservatives had come to the conclusion that cultural representations had significant political ramifications. As a result, the notion that culture held power became a defining characteristic of late 20th-century conservative ideology (Hartman, 2015, p.171).

In the 2000s, culture wars continued on issues including same-sex marriage, stem cell research, education, and the teaching of evolution in schools. The emergence of social media and cable news outlets also amplified the voices of many groups and fuelled America's cultural wars. With political polarisation escalating the severity of the debates, culture wars continue to rage today over topics like immigration, racial justice, and gender identity. While some believe that the culture wars are ending or evolving in new ways, others contend that racial and ethnic conflicts will continue to shape American society for many more years to come.

Impact of Culture Wars on the Political System of the US.

Culture Wars have become a defining feature of American politics, greatly influencing the electoral process, which is evident in a variety of socio-political issues, such as abortion, same-sex marriage, gun control, and immigration. They have also dominated political campaigns, creating a highly partisan and contentious political environment. As a result, the political debate is getting increasingly heated and is no longer limited to particular policy issues but reflects the more fundamental cultural divides that underlie it.

The Democrats and Republicans are becoming increasingly polarised on cultural issues like abortion, same-sex marriage, immigration, gun control, and gender roles with each party representing one of the two

opposing worldviews, progressivism or traditionalism. Consequently, it becomes difficult to find a solution to problems that were formerly considered non-partisan, such as social welfare and environmental protection, which are highly politicised and ideologically charged. This polarisation has created two distinct camps among voters, making it more difficult for politicians to gain support from a broad array of voters.

According to a 2020 Pew Research Centre study, the US has more ideological conflicts over cultural issues than the UK, France, and Germany (Silver, 2021). The study measured the opinions of individuals on a range of topics, including abortion, gender roles, and same-sex marriage among others, and found that the ideological differences between Americans were far greater than those in the other countries surveyed. For instance, when asked if same-sex marriage should be allowed, 61 per cent of Americans responded in favour of it, but there was a substantial ideological gap in this position. While 83 per cent of Democrats supported same-sex marriage, only 34 per cent of Republicans agreed. In comparison, in the UK, France, and Germany, there was much greater agreement on this issue, with support for same-sex marriage ranging from 71 per cent to 82 per cent across the three countries.

Furthermore, both Democrats and Republicans used cultural issues, particularly those related to education, critical race theory, transgender rights, and immigration to mobilise their base and appeal to swing voters in the US mid-term elections of 2022. These issues shaped the political discourse leading up to the elections and the polarisation of opinion between the two parties made it difficult for candidates to appeal to independent and moderate voters (Jones, 2022). Additionally, there have been reports that Republicans are promoting “parental rights” in education to fuel the on-going culture war, and some perceive it as a part of a broader effort to mobilise conservative voters ahead of the 2024 presidential elections (Gambino, 2023).

Culture Wars have also exacerbated the urban-rural divide in the US with political polarisation visible in urban and local voters. Urban areas tend to be more Democratic-leaning, while rural areas tend to be more Republican-leaning. Urban and rural areas, with different regions, tend to have vastly different political priorities and interests. Urban areas tend

to be more diverse, liberal, and globalised, while rural areas tend to be more homogenous, conservative, and traditional. As a result, how candidates appeal to urban and rural voters also varies as different issues and concerns drive these areas.

A case in point is the 2016 presidential elections, in which the candidates built their rhetoric around issues like jobs and economy in rural areas and social justice and equality in urban areas. Moreover, an analysis of precinct data from the election illustrates this urban-rural divide. In the 2016 presidential elections, Hillary Clinton won most urban counties while Donald Trump won most rural counties (Badger, 2019). Thus, cultural wars in America are found in electoral politics, widening the urban-rural divide.

The rise of identity politics in the US has also been linked to culture wars, with different groups mobilising around their particular cultural or ethnic identities. As a result, various interest groups vie for political influence and power, sometimes at the expense of a shared national identity (Hamid, 2022). Moreover, cultural issues like abortion, gun rights, and immigration have become more important to voters than economic issues, and the trend is likely to continue (Kaufmann, 2022). Identity politics has thus become an important strategy of the Democrats and Republicans to rally their support base and come into power.

Culture Wars have also significantly contributed to the decline in trust in institutions such as the federal government, media, and corporations which can affect their effective functioning. There is a perception that institutions are aligned with one side. For example, institutions that promote progressive values, such as the media and universities, have been accused of being biased and out of touch with mainstream values. On the other hand, institutions that are seen as promoting conservative values, such as religious institutions and some parts of government, have been accused of being intolerant and exclusionary.

A survey conducted by Pew Research Centre in 2019 to assess the levels of trust and distrust among Americans towards different institutions such as the federal government, media, and each other found that Americans had low levels of trust in these institutions, with trust in the federal government being particularly low (Rainie et al., 2019). Moreover, the study also revealed that Democrats tended to show more trust in these institutions than Republicans. Additionally, the survey found that

Americans had varying levels of trust in each other based on race, ethnicity, and education.

Cultural wars have also led to the rise of populism (International Affairs Forum, n.d.) and the erosion of democratic values (Stanton, 2021), such as respect for the rule of law, free and fair elections, and peaceful transfer of power in the US. They have created a sense of grievance among certain segments of the population who feel attacked by the federal government, media, and other institutions. Moreover, previously non-partisan issues like education and science are being politicised leading to a rejection of expertise and informed policymaking.

Populist politicians exploit these grievances and claim to represent the “forgotten” majority and to address their concerns if brought to power. They often portray their opponents as enemies of the people or illegitimate and seek to undermine the legitimacy of democratic institutions to consolidate power. A case in point is the Capital Riots of 6 January 2020, when a mob sought to impede a peaceful transfer of power from incumbent President Donald Trump by preventing a joint session of Congress from counting the electoral votes to formalise the victory of President-elect Joe Biden.

Thus, culture wars have had a major impact on US’ political landscape, polarising, fracturing, and intensifying the ideological climate. Even though there is no easy solution to these problems, the US must address these issues to create a more cohesive and inclusive political system that can meet the interests and concerns of all Americans.

A Political Perspective on Abortion Rights

The debate over abortion rights has made states the key battleground where this culture war is played out (Mouw & Sobel, 2001, p.913). With heated debates between those who favour and those who oppose the right to abortion in the US, the issue has been highly politicised. Political parties and politicians have taken strong stances on the matter, but the topic remains highly controversial and divisive.

There was no national abortion policy in the US before 1973, and the states had complete autonomy in this regard. Although a few states had liberalised their abortion laws in the previous decade, the majority continued their restrictive policies in compliance with legislation from

the nineteenth century (McKeever, 2008, p.224). In the early 20th century, abortion in the US was largely illegal (Mouw & Sobel, 2001, p.919). Before *Roe v. Wade*, many states had criminalised abortion, making it difficult or impossible for women to obtain safe and legal abortions (Brennan Centre for Justice, 2022). Abortion rights received federal protection for nearly fifty years (Blazina, 2022) through the landmark judgment in *Roe v. Wade* in 1973. It established a woman's constitutional right to abortion up to the point of foetal viability.

The judgment has been the subject of numerous legal challenges over the years, but the basic right to abortion remained intact despite many state courts imposing restrictions on abortions (Brennan Centre for Justice, 2022). Some argue that such laws are often motivated by political ideology rather than medical or public health concerns (Brennan Centre for Justice, 2022).

The Supreme Court's decision to overturn the judgment in June 2022 has made the states the legal battleground for abortion rights and invited a variety of responses (The Associated Press, 2022). Many states in the US, such as Alabama, Texas, Georgia, Missouri, Ohio, and Mississippi, have passed laws in the last five years restricting access to abortion by banning it after a certain point in pregnancy. However, such laws have been challenged in court. Additionally, other states such as Missouri, South Dakota, North Dakota, Utah, and Arkansas have passed laws that restrict access to abortion by imposing waiting periods, mandatory counselling, mandatory ultrasounds, and other requirements (The Associated Press, 2022).

According to a Pew Research Centre survey conducted in June 2022, the majority of Americans disagree with the Supreme Court's decision to overturn *Roe v. Wade*. Only 41 per cent of Americans, according to the study, supported the court's ruling, while 57 per cent disagreed. Additionally, it showed a significant partisan divide between Democrats and Republicans, with 82 per cent of Democrats and Democratic-leaning independents strongly opposing the decision and 70 per cent of Republicans and GOP leaners largely supporting it (Pew Research Centre, 2022).

The Republican-Democratic divide once again became evident when the respondents were questioned on whether or not abortion should be legal in all or most cases. Only 38 per cent of Republicans agreed, nearly the

same as the 39 per cent who participated in the survey in 2007, compared to 84 per cent of Democrats, up from 72 per cent in 2016 and 63 per cent in 2007. Thus, it can be concluded that the Republicans' stance on abortion rights has more or less remained the same and the recent widening of the partisan gap is largely driven by the Democrats (Pew Research Centre, 2022).

There is also a divide within the two parties, on the matter of legality of abortion. Conservative and moderate Democrats make up around 77 per cent of those who think abortion should be permitted in most or all circumstances. Similarly, 92 per cent of liberal Democrats concur with this. The two groups differ significantly, with just 34 per cent of conservative and moderate Democrats agreeing that abortion should be permitted in all circumstances, compared to 59 per cent of liberal Democrats. Conservative Republicans and Republican-leaning independents differ significantly from moderate and liberal Republicans in their views on abortion. 73 per cent of conservative Republicans and Republican-leaning independents believe abortion should be illegal in most or all cases. In comparison, 60 per cent of moderate and liberal Republicans believe that abortion should be permitted in most or all circumstances (Pew Research Centre, 2022).

Additionally, when it comes to the question of the morality of abortion, 68 per cent of Republicans, or the majority, think that having an abortion is morally wrong in most or all circumstances. On the other hand, just about 29 per cent of Democrats share this opinion. Around 40 per cent of Democrats believe that having an abortion is morally acceptable in most or all circumstances. Additionally, it is a non-moral issue for 28 per cent of Democrats (Pew Research Centre, 2022).

Therefore, within both Democrats and Republicans, there is disagreement on the legality and morality of abortion, with more liberal members of both parties being more supportive of abortion rights and their moral acceptability when compared to conservatives and moderates. Moreover, it can be observed that there is a shift in opinion among Democrats towards greater support for abortion rights, and this has been the main driver of the widening partisan gap with the Republicans. Furthermore, contrary to conservative Republicans and Republican-leaning independents, moderate and liberal Republicans are more likely to support abortion rights and consider it to be morally acceptable.

Additionally, it can be pointed out that public opinion on abortion rights is becoming more polarised along party lines with the Democrats backing it and the Republicans opposing it.

Impact on Federalism, Separation of Powers and Party System in the US.

The issue of abortion rights has impacted federalism, separation of powers, and the US party system by affecting the larger political and legal structures. There have been legal disputes over the scope of state v. federal regulation of abortion, leading to a conflict between the legislative and judicial branches of government. Additionally, the two major political parties have become increasingly divided over the abortion debate, making it more challenging for politicians to find common ground on other issues of concern.

Federalism

Federalism has played a significant role in the abortion debate in the US since its inception. The constitutional right to an abortion was established in 1973 by the landmark case of *Roe v. Wade*. Nevertheless, several states have attempted to impose restrictions or outright bans on abortion, including parental consent laws, mandatory counselling requirements, and waiting periods. This has led to legal disputes regarding the extent of state versus federal authority over abortion in the US, bringing to light the conflicting interests of the federal and state governments.

For example, the Supreme Court in “*Planned Parenthood of Southeastern Pennsylvania v. Casey*” invalidated parts of a Texas law that required clinics to adhere to the same standards as surgical centres and required abortion providers to have admitting privileges at a nearby hospital in 2016 (Liptak, 2016). The court held that the law placed an undue burden on a woman’s right to choose an abortion and was, therefore, unconstitutional. A case from Mississippi that challenged the constitutional right to abortion was established by *Roe v. Wade* in 1973 (Pittman, 2022) and was struck down by a lower court as unconstitutional. The state then asked the Supreme Court to overturn *Roe v. Wade* and allow states to regulate or ban abortion as they see fit.

Some argue that, in the US, the federal system has allowed states to enact a patchwork of regulations that create significant disparities in access to abortion (McKeever, 2008, p.225). Moreover, federal funding restrictions have impacted women's access to reproductive healthcare. The joint federal-state Medicaid programs are a case in point and have led to the withholding of abortion funds for indigent women (McKeever, 2008, p.230). Thus, cooperative federalism in the US suffers when the priorities of states and the federal government collide over the extension of abortion rights to citizens.

Separation of Powers

The concept of separation of powers is a fundamental principle of the US political system. However, the debate over abortion rights has adversely affected this balance by causing a conflict of opinion between the legislative and judicial branches. Conservatives contend that the Supreme Court overstepped its bounds in *Roe v. Wade* by creating a right not explicitly stated in the US Constitution, leading to a call for judicial restraint and greater emphasis on the legislature's role in formulating policy.

Cases such as *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organisation* and *Cameron v. EMW Women's Surgical Centre* have called into question this concept of separation of powers (Slattery & Meese, 2020). In *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organisation*, the Supreme Court was presented with an opportunity to revisit and overturn the earlier 1973 *Roe v. Wade* ruling and return the issue of abortion rights to the states. Again, in *Cameron v. EMW Women's Surgical Centre*, the question of separation of powers was brought up as it involved the authority of the state government to regulate medical facilities and the ability of the judiciary to intervene in these decisions.

While Congress has often tried to uphold the constitutional right to abortion, the US Supreme Court has stood for the accommodation of state and local viewpoints with respect to abortion rights (McKeever, 2008, p.236). Thus, the Supreme Court, until the overturning of *Roe v. Wade* protected a woman's constitutional right to abortion; however, beyond that, it left the matter to the states. Furthermore, by overruling *Roe v. Wade* and *Planned Parenthood of Southeastern Pennsylvania v. Casey* in 2022, the US Supreme Court has put constraints on Congress's authority to regulate abortion (Congressional Research Service, 2022, p.1).

Additionally, recent Supreme Court decisions on gun rights and abortion indicate a shift towards conservative maximalism among the court's judges, bringing into question the separation of powers between the federal and state governments (Hurley, 2022). The court decided to uphold a Mississippi law that bans abortions after 15 weeks of pregnancy in the *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organisation* case which eventually led to the overturning of *Roe v. Wade*.

Party System

Abortion has become a polarising issue within the two major political parties in the US. The Democrats and Republicans remain largely divided on the issue with the former advocating a pro-choice and the latter a pro-life stance. It has contributed to the widening partisan divide between the two parties and increased polarisation of views. As a result, finding a middle ground and negotiating on other issues has become more challenging for the two parties.

The Republican Party has typically adopted a more conservative stance on abortion, with many of its members calling for restrictions or complete bans on the procedure. On the contrary, the Democratic Party has long been more supportive of abortion rights, with many of its members advocating for greater accessibility to safe and legal abortions. Because of this, the issue of abortion has emerged as a major point of contention between the two parties, with many politicians utilising it to rally their support base and win over swing voters (Hare & Poole, 2014, p.418).

Thus, abortion rights have had a significant impact on federalism, separation of powers, and the party system of the US. The issue remains decisive in US politics with several factions continuing to push for their respective views and policies.

Conclusion

Culture Wars have their roots in the organising principle of American pluralism. However, during the 1960s and 1970s, they intensified as a result of cultural and social developments in the US, including the civil rights movement, the sexual revolution, and the rise of the counterculture. Through the years, culture wars have evolved and shifted, with both new issues and debates emerging. The argument over

abortion rights, which has been at the centre of the US culture wars since the 1970s, is now joined by issues such as affirmative action, LGBTQ rights, and immigration.

Culture Wars have had a major impact on the US political system. They have influenced the electoral process by dominating political campaigns and creating two distinct camps of voters. With political polarisation visible in urban and rural voters, culture wars have also exacerbated the urban-rural divide in America. The rise of identity politics and populism in the US can also be linked to culture wars. Besides, they have also significantly contributed to the decline in trust in institutions in the US, affecting their effective functioning.

From a political perspective, the issue of abortion rights has been fiercely debated for years, with both pro-choice and pro-life factions strongly defending their positions. It has exacerbated the partisan divide between the two major political parties and led to increased polarisation. Additionally, it is observed that there is a shift in opinion among Democrats towards greater support for abortion rights which is the main driver of the widening partisan gap with Republicans.

The debate over abortion rights has also had a significant impact on federalism, separation of powers, and party system in the US. Due to the federal system of government, each state now has its own patchwork of laws, with some adopting more stringent laws than others. Additionally, there have been legal disputes between the legislative and judicial branches over the issue. As indicated by the decision to overturn *Roe v. Wade*, there has been a trend towards conservative maximalism within the judiciary, perceived as an attempt by the judiciary to limit Congress' ability to regulate abortion.

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